

REFLECTING THE IMAGE OF OUR ANCESTORS IN THE SCULPTURAL ART OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article describes in detail the image of our ancestors in the sculptural art of Uzbekistan, the symbolic-philosophical solution of the statue, monumental sculpture, the development of monumental sculpture in connection with social development.

Key words: sculpture, monumental sculpture, social development.

Introduction:

The symbolic-philosophical solution of the statue: represents peace and tranquility, justice and creativity. Also, as a symbolic tool for the figure of a great person, it reflects the development of a new independent society under the spiritual support of powerful ancestors. In addition, there is another philosophical content of the image. For example, the artistic image of Sahibqiran was embodied in an expressive way that eliminated unjust views promoted during the period of autocracy. In this form, artistic expressiveness is embodied, which fundamentally denies all the artificial views of the former regime.

Literature analysis and methodology:

On the monument, the righteous commander wisely raises his hand without a sword and wishes for peace and security to the people of the world. After all, in the interpretation of the general form, the national revival, the patriotic virtues of our ancestors, as well as the inculcation of the perfect qualities of their psyche into the psyche of our people, symbolic connections of the past and the new era are reflected.

Amir Temur's luxurious appearance reveals his personality traits. According to its compositional structure, Uzbekistan is embodied in the shape of a saffron, which symbolizes the independence of the state.

Independence and goodness - realizes the responsibility of preserving our ancestral values like the apple of an eye and passing them on to future generations. The Independence and Virtue Monument is a rare and immortal monument dedicated to the creative potential of our people, loyalty to the great history, always striving for a bright destination with hope and confidence, strong will and high moral spirit.

Results:

The monument "Independence and Virtue" is made in the position of holding a young baby in his hands (bronze, size 9 meters). The image of a woman carrying a baby is a common theme throughout the world. The sculptor created the image of the Uzbek Madonna in sculpture through this statue. Looking at her baby with loving eyes, the mother's eyes are filled with gratitude, hope and confidence for the future, and happiness.

Monumental statues are designed to be seen from afar. In this regard, we see statues of our great ancestors in all cities of our republic. The works of famous masters of the art of

sculpture in Uzbekistan, especially Abdumomin Boymatov, Ilhom Jabbarov, Jaloliddin Mirtojiyev, Anvar Rahmatullayev and several other sculptors, attract the attention of many. Sculpting is described through methods of processing and details and forms that have a certain volume in nature. It also has a type of "Elegant Sculpture". This method is called domestic plastic in sculpture. Fine sculptures are distinguished by their elegance and small size. It can be captured. Porcelain, ceramics, wood, metals and expensive types of stones, like ivory, are used in elegant sculpture.

Monumental sculpture is a type of sculpture related to architecture and urban planning. According to its appearance, it is divided into round and rounded types. Monumental sculptural works express great meaning and have an independent social character, and are directly combined with the environment and architectural buildings. Because his works are intended to be viewed from a distance, large, solid forms are widely used; Monumental sculptures are placed on squares, parks, avenues, streets, etc., as well as sculptures on building walls. Monumental sculpture includes monuments, memorials, sculptural complexes, as well as works of decorative sculpture erected to perpetuate the memory of important historical events, famous people. The color of the work is determined by the raw material used for the sculpture.

Discussion:

Monumental sculpture developed in connection with social development. Qad. It occupies an important place in Egypt, Western Asia, India, China and other eastern countries. Rare examples of it were created in Greece and Rome. The Middle Ages played an important role in the art of European countries: cathedrals, temples, and the surrounding squares were decorated with sculptures. During the renaissance, examples of monumental sculpture, imbued with humanitarian ideas, were developed, enriched with new content and elegant ideas in the 17th-20th centuries.

In the territory of Central Asia, many archeological monuments of the Neolithic period have been found and studied, which allows us to get enough information about the ornament and visual art of our primitive ancestors. In the Joytun culture, a Neolithic settlement in southern Turkmenistan, BC. 30 houses dating back to the VI-V millennia were excavated and studied. The houses were built with one room from large flat-convex bricks based on the plan. The outer and inner walls of the houses are plastered with clay and painted with ocher. Work tools, geometrically shaped flint sickles, bow arrowheads, axes, bone needles and polishing tools were found at the site.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the findings of Sopollitepa are unique sources that provide valuable information about the history of culture, art and architecture of our ancient ancestors. In the study of the art and architecture of the ancient people of Central Asia, the settlement of Jarqo'ton occupies a special place. Since 1973, it has been excavated by members of the expedition led by archaeologist A. Askarov. The remains of a settlement, a temple, a pottery neighborhood, metal smelting workshops, and more than 1,000 graves were discovered in Jarko'ton.

References:

1. Oripov B. Fine art and its teaching methodology. -T.: "Ilm Ziya", 2006.

2. Abdirasilov S.F. Fine art methodology. -T., "Ilm-Ziya", 2006.
3. Boymetov B.B., Abdirasilov S.F. Draftsman. -T., "Gafur Ghulam", 2004.
4. Kadirkho'jayev P. Decorative art. -T., "Economics and finance, 2007.
5. Bulatov S., Mansurov O'. Philosophy of applied art in national architecture. Tashkent, 2005.

